

ROLE OF MEN AND WOMEN IN FAMILY RELATIONS.

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The family, which is the main unit of society, is based on the relationship between a man and a woman. In this regard, the duties and tasks assigned to the spouses have been in the center of constant discussions. The issue of men and women has been a controversial issue at all times and places. We consider it permissible to dwell here on the points where the most problems arise.

Family, conjugal relations are considered a sacred bond in our religion. There are big goals in building this relationship and building a family. For this reason, both parties are assigned their respective responsibilities, duties, and tasks. First of all, it is necessary to understand what is the purpose of starting a family. In our Sharia, every work has a purpose. In our religion, it is important to protect a person's life, mind, religion, honor, and property, and accordingly regulations are introduced. The purpose of marriage is to preserve chastity, which means that both parties must preserve each other's chastity. Another main goal is procreation. Creating a peaceful family is one of the goals, and if the family is peaceful, the society will be peaceful. The potential of society depends on the potential of families.

Husband's duties to his wife: In the family, a man's duty to his wife is divided into two parts: material and spiritual duties. Financial duties include the maintenance of a woman. Starting with giving a dowry to a woman and building a family, all her needs are met: food, clothing, shelter, if she can afford it, if the woman finds it difficult to do housework, providing her with a helper, household furniture, and necessary items for cleanliness. It is a man's duty to provide. He should do this for his wife without pain.

Spiritual duties include giving knowledge to a woman, strengthening her religion, treating her well, and leading a good life.

Duties of a woman to her husband: The basis of a woman's duties to her husband is her obedience. It is the duty of a woman not to fast without her husband's permission, not to let people her husband does not like into her house, not to give things in the house to someone without his permission, to protect her husband's secrets, to protect her family members and children.

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Relations with loved ones: Both parties should respect each other's loved ones and family members and have good relations. This situation is often violated by men. When a woman goes to her husband's house, she respects his family members and relatives, otherwise a conflict will quickly arise. There are also women who allow themselves to do this, and this is one of the reasons why the husband is disappointed and cold. That is probably why the role of the head of the family in the family is different for the man, and the role of the mistress of the family is for the woman. Other, in some sense, duties and responsibilities are also distributed.

Despite this, when it comes to men and women, or more precisely, when considering their relationship, the question "What does a woman want?" or "What does a man need?" such lively questions appear. First of all, this is natural. Men and women are such entities that still have many unexplored and unexplored aspects... In short, today's comments are addressed to my peers, that is, men, and we will try to open (recognize) the magical doors of the stronger sex. We do not have some thoughts to say to our respectable women, such as "my daughter, I will tell you, my daughter-in-law, you listen".

It is known that the desire of men depends on his mood (mental state), health (physical state) and social (spiritual and economic) state.

Despite being the representatives of the stronger sex, men are quickly broken mentally, prone to depression, and have the "ability" to destroy the fortress built over the years by riding a single angry horse with a single word.

Their spiritual world needs constant attention, love, wise advice and praise as an incentive for their work! However, there are men who do not feel the need for attention and kindness from women (except for sexual needs) for life. as long as they can live, even living alone is not considered a tragedy for them. It is not difficult to meet some people who, in the vernacular, have "left the world". According to psychologists, men judge women primarily by looking at their faces. Almost all representatives of the stronger sex "create" a woman's figure based on her facial structure. The same "face" can cause men to "turn away" from women.

It is better to be a little more careful when it comes to height, because different men like women of different heights. Someone is fat, someone is full, someone is tall, someone is short... According to psychologists from Yevpora, men pay attention to the level of proportion of women's stature. However, for 50% of men, height does not matter. What is important is the spiritual world of a woman who

has opened her eyes! His attitude towards his spouse and family! Women's hair, hairstyle, meaningful feeding, skin color, breasts, hips and gait, etc. .

However, this very impression can be chipped by a single "small sign". For example, if long nails are painted with shiny, unattractive paint, a charming face and a pleasant smile are "disrupted" by crooked, unkempt and "black spot" decayed teeth. , a beautiful woman suddenly opens her mouth and laughs, or a woman who preaches about values and education drinks alcohol and smokes cigarettes, etc. p. Men don't like women who are too revealing and show some parts of their body...